

The Implementation of *Manunggaling Kawula – Gusti* Concept in Baluwarti Settlement's Spatial Layout in Kasunanan Surakarta Palace during Paku Buwono III's Reign (1749-1788)

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Abstract

Baluwarti settlement was selected to be the object of research, because the settlement is a part of Kasunanan Surakarta Palace region, constituting the source of Surakarta Javanese culture. The existence of it is arranged and grouped by status, role, and rank of individual dwellers. This settlement was formerly the capital of Surakarta Hadiningrat Kingdom. The settlement pattern in Baluwarti neighborhoods can be seen from the division of territory, dwelling area corresponding to the top-down social class. Thus, this research is aimed at exploring the early concept of this settlement construction. The research method used was qualitative method historical reading approach, and then data analysis was conducted inductively referring to grounded theory through the process of analyzing data conducted from data raw coding to concept or theory development stages. The concept of Baluwarti settlement's spatial layout constructed during Paku Buwana III time is the manifestation of values and cultural traditions of the Palace, "Manunggaling Kawula-Gusti". It can be seen from the function of spatial layout created, the relationship between the King and the people/subjects, so that the spatial layout is embodied as a security system, a tradition preserving system, and the King-serving system.

Keywords: *Concept, Spatial Layout, Baluwarti Settlement, Manunggaling Kawula – Gusti*

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Surakarta City is selected to be the location of research, because this city is known as one of Javanese culture center, and because traditionally, Surakarta is one of Javanese traditional development centers. The existence of Surakarta city is inseparable from the existence of two traditional rule centers: Kasunanan Surakarta and Kadipaten Mangkunegaran Palaces. Surakarta or Solo/Sala City grew along with the movement of Islamic Mataram Kingdom's Capital from Kartasura in 1745. As a Capital of Kingdom, the palace (court) where the king resides is a center encircled with fortress as a "state" or *negari*. The fortress encircling Kasunanan Surakarta Palace was called *Baluwarti*. Then, to support the king's rule, Sunan Paku Buwono III (PB III) created area surrounding *Kedhaton* as the defense area. The area surrounding the court, called *Baluwarti*, was functioned to be the settlement of people, particularly the relative of king, and the people becoming the King's servants, such as princess, king's relative/*sentana dalem* and *abdi dalem* (Soeratman, 1989:32).

The elements of settlement, such as spatial layout pattern (physical aspect) and social cultural life tradition with any rites (non-physical aspect) are still maintained/undertaken by most people in Baluwarti settlement until today, resulting in distinctive peculiarity. It is this

peculiarity that makes Baluwarti neighborhood located inside the court different from other settlements (outside the court) in Surakarta.

1.2. Problem Statement

Considering the background above, the existence of Surakarta Palace, trusted as the Javanese cultural center, is still expected by Surakarta and surrounding people, although physically some buildings inside the court area have changed. The dwelling was grouped by status, role, and rank (grade) of individual dwellers. Baluwarti settlement is believed to have concept originating from the court's traditional tradition and culture (Javanese culture) as the elements composing the typical spatial layout of settlement. The problem statement of current research is: How is the early concept of Baluwarti settlement's spatial layout plan constructed during Paku Buwono III's reign (1749-1788)?

1.3. Objective

The objectives of research are to interpret the concept of Baluwarti settlement's spatial layout in the beginning of settlement construction, and to reveal traditional and cultural values as the elements composing the typical spatial layout of settlement based on historical study. Thus, local wisdom values are obtained to build local concept/theory becoming the reference to formulate self identity of Indonesian settlement architecture.

2. Method

Meanwhile, the research method used was inductive qualitative one with historical reading method. Historical reading was used to find out the early concept of Baluwarti settlement's spatial layout constructed during PB III's reign, through books or *babad* telling the condition at that time, document/archive/magazine/article, and newspaper, figure of that period, and artifacts still existing. The application of historical reading approach here referred to historical research. Figure 1. shows the chart of historical reading working method the author would use as the reference in the field.

Figure 1. Work Method of Historical Reading
(Source: analysis, 2016)

3. Result And Discussion

KGPH Dipokusuma (2016) states that the construction of settlement for soldiers was one of priorities, because they served to safeguard the king's safety, and at that time there was trauma with the rebellion occurring in Kartasura that destroyed the Court. Then, there was also the rebellion of RM Said along with his followers, so the presence of soldiers as the king's safeguarding tool was very desirable. *Tamtama* and *Carang* (lower-ranking noncommissioned) soldiers served to safeguard the King, while *Wireng* soldier served to safeguard the organization of ceremony/tradition held by the court. Thus, in the beginning of construction in Baluwarti settlement area, the settlements for *Tamtama*, *Carang*, and *Wireng* soldiers were prioritized first.

Figure 2. Physical Condition of Baluwarti Settlement during PB.III (1749-1788 AD)
(Source: Pustaka Radya Laksana, and Hardiyanti, 2004)

3.1. Non-Physical Elements of Region

At that time Javanese people still considered that the center of world is the king and the court, God is the center of macrocosm, while the king is considered as the representative of God and the center of community in the world. In macrocosmic scale, king is God's representative with court as his residence. The court (Palace) is the sacred center of kingdom and king is considered as the source of cosmic powers flowing into his sovereignty region and brings composure, justice, and fertility into his region.

In social life, most people in Baluwarti settlement were *sentana dalem* and *abdi dalem*, working for/serving the king. Thus, nearly all of Baluwarti people had title conferred by the King. Social status of Baluwarti people was obtained hereditarily from their lineage, social status of Surakarta Palace's nobilities. In addition to the form of *trah* (lineage) name, there is some other thing sent down hereditarily, land and building on it. If an individual having

genetic relation with the court passed away, his/her descent will get inheritance from his/her parents in the form of *magersari* land and building. Such the process proceeds continuously until the last generation of the family *trah*.

Figure 3. The exploration of Non-Physical Elements by Variable and their effect on Baluwarti Settlement's Spatial Layout

Non physical elements affect or create the spatial layout pattern of Baluwarti settlement. The physical characteristics of settlement's spatial layout affected by non-physical elements are as follows:

- a) Site/region is encircled by Baluwarti fortress, thereby is protected from the enemy.
- b) Cosmological orientation includes four cardinal points or cardinal directions.
- c) Zoning, the closer to *kedhaton* (the king) the area, the higher is the sacred value.
- d) Regional orientation is to region center/*kedhaton*.
- e) Circulation pattern/road network encircling the *kedhaton*/king.
- f) Dwelling pattern is in grid pattern
- g) The form of dwelling building is adjusted with status and title.

3.2. Physical Elements of Region

Baluwarti settlement is located in the second ring, close to the first ring in which the king resides. The court area is divided concentrically according to Behrend (1982). The second ring (circle) has high magic aura, as it is close to the first one, *kedhaton*.

Located in the second ring, this settlement has strong magic aura as it is close to the king. *Abdi dalem/kawula* is desirable to the king, thereby is given a place very close to the king. It confirms that the king wants to always be close to his *kawula*/people. Considering the data constituting the information resulting from interview with some informants, it can be found

that physical elements of Baluwarti Settlement's spatial layout in the beginning of its construction are:

- a. Building including: Baluwarti fortress, grid-shaped road network, *Kori Brajanala Utara* and *Kori Brajanala Selatan*, Settlement for abdi dalem or *Tamtama*, *Carang*, and *Wireng* soldiers, and Ki Gede Sala's grave.
- b. Formation of Baluwarti settlement in the beginning of its construction was affected by *sedulur papat kalima pancer* concept, consisting of North, East, South, and West parts, with nearly equal size except for the west part. Meanwhile, *kedhaton* as the center/*pancer* of the four cardinal points. The composition of direction - North - South and East-West - is also the manifestation of dualism/*loroning atunggal* concept. The access to settlement area is located in the center of area, in the North and in the South.
- c. Pattern
The pattern of Baluwarti settlement form is circling and oriented to *kedhaton* (as the King's position). It indicates that there is a close relationship between settlement area and *kedhaton*. Thus, this settlement was devised to encircle the *kedhaton* area concentrically.

Figure 4. shows the analysis on the relationship between physical elements of settlement's spatial layout explored based on variables from the result of theoretical study. Physical elements affect or create the spatial layout pattern of Baluwarti settlement.

Figure 4. The exploration of physical elements by variable and their effect on Spatial Layout of Baluwarti Settlement

Systematically, the development of spatial layout concept using grounded theory is so called data theorization, in which theory or concept was developed from the bottom data as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Process of Constructing Baluwarti Settlement Concept

Considering the analysis on both physical and non-physical aspects constituting the components of settlement's spatial layout and on the concepts underlying the spatial layout, it can be found that the design of Baluwarti settlement's spatial layout during PB.III's reign is the one created as defense and security, tradition preserving, and serving-king systems.

3.2.1. Spatial Layout of Settlement as Defense and Security System

The spatial layout of Baluwarti Settlement is created as the defense system as manifested in the physical elements, as follows: a) Baluwarti fortress, the existence of which encircles the region with thickness and height that can guarantee the safety and defense against enemy, b) *kori Brajanala*, constituting the limited entry and exit access that is always safeguarded by soldiers, and these gates are always closed at night, c) dwelling pattern in grid pattern, creating the life defense space of people (*kawula/abdi dalem*) residing in this region, d) form of dwelling pattern encircling *kedhaton* concentrically also creates defense space.

Meanwhile, the non-physical elements creating defense system are: a) infinite trust in the King's power/rule. The people's trust in a king who has power higher than ordinary people gives them the feeling of secure, b) the conferral of title to the people with certain status will grow the feeling of being responsible for the security of Baluwarti environment/region.

Figure 6. Spatial Layout of Settlement as Security Sistem

3.2.2. Spatial Layout of settlement as the Tradition and Culture Preserving System

The spatial layout of Baluwarti settlement is created as the system of preserving tradition and culture, as manifested into physical elements as follows: a) the shape of dwelling for *abdi dalem*, *sentana dalem* and *dalem pangeran* has Javanese traditional style, adjusted with the status of dwellers. The dweller with high stratum occupies Joglo-shaped house, while *abdi dalem* occupies the *limasan*/kampong-shaped house, b) the people living inside Baluwarti fortress have obligation different from that of people outside, in which the people inside have regulation specified by the king/the court, c) the presence of Ki Gede Sala's Grave in Baluwarti environment is the manifestation of or the expression of respect to his merit to Surakarta Palace in giving his region to the construction of court.

Figure 7. Spatial Layout of Settlement as Tradition Preserving System

The non-physical elements of spatial layout embodying the tradition and culture preserving system are: a) microcosmic-macrocosmic belief, Hindu religion tenet, and Islam religion tenet teaching human beings to keep maintaining the relationship between fellow human beings and between them and Almighty God, b) norms held in society life originating from the court's norms, applied according to the condition, and c) the court's tradition and culture, in which Baluwarti people are the performers of the court's tradition and rite, corresponding to the king's order (command). In addition, the people also implement the rite imitating what has been implemented by the court, corresponding to their condition.

3.2.3. *Spatial Layout of Settlement as the Serving-King System*

The spatial layout of Baluwarti settlement is created as the system of serving the king as embodied in the physical elements as follows: a) road network, created encircling and oriented to *kedhaton*/palace/king, thereby the king/the palace's need can be afforded or can be fulfilled more quickly and easily, b) the group-dwelling pattern with grid pattern of road network facilitates the leader to coordinate his subordinates, c) the pattern of *abdi dalem* dwelling grouped by skill also facilitates and accelerates the coordination, and d) settlement site/region encircling *kedhaton*/king facilitates the service delivery to every corner.

The non-physical elements contributing to creating serving-king system are: a) *magersari* system, the one governing the duty and obligation of those becoming *abdi dalem*, in which the people serving the King get dwelling that can be sent down to their descents, b) economic system occurring during Paku Buwana III's reign is a sub-system economy in which people produce materials and tools according to the king and family's need.

Figure 8. *Spatial Layout of Settlement as Serving-King System*

4. Conclusion and Acknowledgment

4.1. Conclusion

Considering the result of analysis conducted on spatial layout concept of Baluwarti settlement constructed by Paku Buwana III, the following conclusions can be drawn. The early concept of Baluwarti settlement's spatial layout is the manifestation of Court's traditional and cultural values "*Manunggaling Kawula – Gusti*" requiring the togetherness between King and his people, moreover when the kingdom was constructed. It can also be seen from the function of

spatial layout inseparable from the relationship established jointly between the king and the people/*kawula*, in realizing the spatial layout as security, tradition preserving, and serving-king systems.

The spatial layout as security system was created by people and king, so that the king and people protect each other and are protected by each other. Meanwhile, the spatial layout as the serving-king system is the reciprocal relation between king and his people in which they are giving and taking from each other.

The conclusion of current research is in line with Subanar (2010:84) suggesting that in leadership ethics, concept of *manunggaling kawula lan Gusti* can also be defined as a leader that should unite with people, to feel the people's life difficulty, rather than only sitting on the glory throne with *dalang-dalang* surrounding.

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